

EMPLOYEE CAREER DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMMES AND ORGANISATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED BANKS IN OJO, LAGOS

DOPAMU, Ifeoluwa Oluwaseyi¹; **JAYEOBA**, Foluso Ilesanmi² & **BONU**, Mariam Pedetin³
^{1,2,3} Department of Industrial Relations and Human Resource Management,
Lagos State University, Ojo. Lagos. Nigeria.
Corresponding author: dopamuifeoluwao@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study examined employee career development programs and organisational performance in selected banks at Ojo, Lagos, Nigeria. The study employed descriptive survey research design, while data were collected through a structured questionnaire administered to sixty-three (63) employees across the selected banks. A combination of purposive and convenience sampling technique was adopted, three hypotheses were formulated and the responses were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) with the aid of SPSS. The findings revealed a strong significant and positive relationships between career counselling, career mentoring and career training on organisational performance. The correlation coefficients specifically showed that career counselling ($r = .791$), career mentoring ($r = .723$), and career training ($r = .752$) each had significant relationship with organisational performance ($p < 0.05$). The study concludes that structured career development programs enhance employee capabilities, efficiency, satisfaction and organizational performance. Hence, it was recommended that the management should institutionalize career counselling, mentoring and continuous training programs to boost workforce competence and retention, thereby improving overall organisational performance.

Keywords: Career Development, Career Counselling, Mentoring, Training, Organisational Performance, Banking Sector.

INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly changing economic environment, employee career development has become important for long-term success. The challenge is no longer just securing a job but adequately managing one's career for sustained employability. According to Delbari *et al.* (2021), the ultimate goal of career development programs is to match employees' aspirations, skills and abilities with existing and future opportunities within the organisation. Employee career development programs is a critical factor in attracting and retaining skilled employees, as organisations must foster a strong and lasting psychological interaction between employees and the organisation (Adamu *et al.*, 2025). Career development is one of the key determinants in retaining competent workers as researchers and professionals submitted that, employees are determined to be more committed in an organisation where they perceived opportunity to advance their career (Keltu, 2024). Aziedjo (2024) underlines that career development programs not only promote employee engagement, but also plays an important role in retaining top talent within an organisation. Similarly, research by Jena and Nayak (2024) reported that organisational career development had

a positive impact on employee retention, with job and organisational engagement serving as partial mediators.

In modern organisations, career development programs range from highly specialized job skill training to comprehensive, long-term professional growth initiatives. Career development is a continuous, lifelong process in which employees participate in a variety of developmental experiences such as career counselling, mentoring, and training to acquire, obtain, and process information concerning their career path. This process involves exploring occupational and educational opportunities, lifestyle preferences, and role alternatives which is influenced by accumulated experience in their particular field of interest (Ubani *et al.*, 2024).

Career development programs are highly beneficial to organisations as they enhance employees' skills, knowledge, and experience, ultimately improving work performance. These programs not only support individual employee growth but also contribute to organisational success. Offering career training opportunities fosters employee loyalty and reduces turnover because employees are more inclined to stay with organisations that contribute to their professional growth (Obaze & Samikon, 2023). Employees are an organisation's most valuable asset, and effectively managing their development is critical to long-term success (Anekwe *et al.*, 2020).

The Nigerian deposit money banks has experienced significant increase in employee turnover from 12.5% in 2018 to 28.1% in 2021 (Chigbundu & Muda, 2022). Recent research further corroborates that this surge is driven by limited career development and weak organisational support, Nwibere (2024) found a strong negative relationship between career advancement opportunities and voluntary turnover, while Bamigboye and Abdulazeez (2023) also highlighted that lack of training, poor performance management, and delayed promotions contributed to talent attrition rate. In the same vein Ejimofor and Ogundare (2023) reported that restricted opportunities for growth is a major cause of high turnover. In light of these conflicting argument and perspective, it is reasonable to realize the need for further research in career development programs and organisational performance, particularly in the banking sector. Therefore, a thorough study and analysis must be undertaken in order to formulate an efficient career development program that would answer the long-term call for individual success and general organisational performance.

Hypotheses Development

Therefore, this study raises the following research hypotheses;

Ho₁: Career counselling does not have significant relationship with organisational performance.

Ho₂: Career mentoring does not have significant relationship with organisational performance.

Ho₃: Career training does not have significant relationship with organisational performance.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Interrogating the relationship that exists between employee career development and organisational performance, this study is anchored/hinged on the human capital theory. The human capital theory which was proposed by Theodore Schultz (1961) and later expanded by Gary Becker (1964) focuses on the critical role played by employees' education, training, and development in enhancing productivity along with the performance of organisations. The theory highlights that the investments in human capital through professional training, education, and skill acquisition generate significant economic returns both for the employee and for the organisation.

According to Schultz (1961), an organisation's emphasis on employee training and development ensures increased productivity, innovation, and long-term growth. In addition, Becker (1964) distinguished between general-purpose human capital that is transferable across organisations and firm-specific human capital, that benefits only the company making the investment. Such a distinction informed contemporary human resources management practices to provide a number of reasons why it is important to make investments in both employee retention strategies and professional development programs.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

In the context of Nigeria banks, previous and several studies have investigated the relationship between career development and employee performance.

Career Counselling and Organisational Performance

Ubani et al. (2024) investigated the effect of career development on employee performance of selected banks in Enugu State. Data were gathered from both primary and secondary source, the survey covered 112 employees from the selected banks. The sample size comprised of 112 randomly selected bank workers. The results showed that career counseling, training, and mentoring had significant effect on employee service quality. The study concluded that career development impacts employee work performance in organisations while recommending that career development be based on realistic and standard practices.

Career Mentoring and Organisational Performance

Igudia (2022) examined the relationship between career development and organisational performance at Palmera Microfinance Bank Ltd, Edo state. The study adopted a survey research design, and data were obtained through questionnaire. Three components were tested using Spearman's Correlation statistical analysis, aided by the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) at 0.05 level of significance. A purposively selected sample of 58 Bank employees was used. The findings demonstrated that career counselling, staff training, and career mentoring all had a strong positive relationship with employee job satisfaction. The study recommended, among other things, that in order for the organisation to achieve optimum productivity, it should implement and design efficient pragmatic employee career development programs that fulfill the expected demands of its employees.

Career Training and Organisational Performance

Udo et al. (2024) explored the relationship between career training and employee performance in money deposit banks in Akwa Ibom State. The study used a descriptive research design, and the population comprising of 200 employees from money deposit banks in Akwa Ibom State. The purposive sample technique was utilized and data were obtained from 200 employees via a

structured questionnaire. The findings revealed that on-the-job training and career mentoring have a positive and significant relationship on employee performance. It was recommended that the management of money deposit banks in Akwa Ibom State money deposit hire and train workers who are likely to get actively involved with the organization's objectives in order to achieve suitable growth and capabilities.

Empirical Gap

Despite these contributions and numerous studies that have been conducted in the area of career development and organisational performance in other parts of Nigeria. However, only few studies by (Aliu & Alenoghena, 2023; Shonubi, 2020) have specifically examined employee career development programmes and organisational performance of deposit money banks in Lagos State. Therefore, this present study seeks to fill this gap by examining employee career development programs and organisational performance of selected banks in Ojo, Lagos State.

METHODS

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study, the population comprised of selected banks in Ojo, Lagos State. However, as at the time of this research only seventy-five (75) employees from three (3) banks which included; UBA, Sterling and Zenith participated in the study. The justification for selecting these banks is premised on the fact that access was given, while other banks did not respond to the request for participation. Due to the relatively small size of the population, the entire population was used as the sample size, this approach ensured that sampling errors and bias were avoided. Hence, sample size determination and calculations were not required. The study utilized a combination of purposive and convenience sampling technique in administering the research instrument to the entire population. Purposive sampling was used to identify the target population which included both permanent and contract staffs within the bank. Likewise, convenience sampling was employed to select participants based on their willingness and availability. A total of seventy-five (75) structured questionnaire were distributed among the selected participants, only sixty-three (63) were successfully retrieved and found fit for analysis representing 84% response rate. The research instrument for the collection of data for this study was a structured questionnaire, there are two sections to the questionnaire. Section A is a detailed characteristic of the respondent demographic information, Section B included career development scale adapted from the organisational career management practices identified by Baruch and Peiperl (2000), specifically isolating the dimensions of mentoring, counselling, and training. The adapted questions and items of the scale measurement of career development programs and organisational performance was equally used in similar studies carried out by (Ubani et al, 2024; Igudiah, 2022). The instrument was based on 5-point Likert scale ranging from 'strongly disagree' (1) to 'strongly agree' (5). The researchers submitted that the instrument yielded a reliable index which is above the benchmark of 0.70. However, for the purpose of this study the instrument reported a Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.86, which shows a high level of internal consistency, therefore it can be established that the instrument is valid and reliable. The statistical analysis employed in this study was the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software editor. All hypotheses were tested using Pearson's Product Moment correlation coefficient to examine the relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

FINDINGS

Table 1: Demographic Analysis of Respondents Variables

S/N	Demographic Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)	
1.	Gender	Male	30	47.6%
		Female	33	52.4%
		Total	63	100
2.	Age	20-29 years	11	17.4%
		30-39 years	43	68.3%
		40 & above	9	14.3%
		Total	63	100
3.	Marital Status	Single	12	19.1%
		Married	46	73.0%
		Others	5	7.9
		Total	63	100
4.	Employment Status	Permanent Staff	38	60.3%
		Contract Staff	25	39.7%
		Total	63	100
5.	Educational Qualification	OND/HND	27	42.9%
		B.Sc	25	39.7%
		M.Sc	11	17.4%
		Total	63	100

Source: Field survey, (2025)

Table 1 shows the descriptive analysis of respondent variables, 47.6% of the respondents are male while the remaining 52.4% were female. Correspondingly, the age distribution indicates that 17.4% of the respondents are within the range of 20-29 years, 68.3% are within age 30-39 years while 14.3% are 40 years and above. Accordingly, the marital status distribution shows that 19.1% of the respondents are Single, 73.0% are Married while Others are 7.9%. Additionally, 60.3% of the total respondents are Permanent staff, while the remaining 39.7% are Contract staff. Also, 42.9% of the respondents are OND/HND holders, 39.7% obtained B.Sc, while 17.4% of the respondents holds M.Sc.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: Career counselling does not have significant relationship with organisation performance.

Table 2: Correlations

		Career Counselling	Organisation Performance
Career Counselling	Pearson Correlation	1	.791**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	63	63
Organisation Performance	Pearson Correlation	.791**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	63	63

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2. above shows the relationship between the dependent and independent variable, the result of the correlation analysis shows a strong positive relationship. The result also shows a 79.1% relationship between career counselling and organisation performance. The result is statistically significant at .005 level of significance ($r=.791, p<.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

H₀₂: Career mentoring does not have significant relationship with organisation performance.

Table 3: Correlations

		Career Mentoring	Organisation Performance
Career Mentoring	Pearson Correlation	1	.723**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	63	63
Organisation Performance	Pearson Correlation	.723**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	63	63

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 above shows the relationship between the dependent and independent variable, the result of the correlation analysis shows a strong and positive relationship. The result also shows a 72.3% relationship between career mentoring and organisation performance. The result is statistically significant at .005 level of significance ($r=.723, p<.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

H03: Career training does not have significant relationship with organisation performance.

Table 4: Correlations

		Career Training	Organisation Performance
Career Training	Pearson Correlation	1	.752**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	63	63
Organisation Performance	Pearson Correlation	.752**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	63	63

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 above shows the relationship between the dependent and independent variable, the result of the correlation analysis shows a strong positive relationship. The result also shows a 75.2% relationship between career training and organisation performance. The result is statistically significant at .005 level of significance ($r=.752, p<.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

DISCUSSION

Based on empirical evidence in the current study as well as previous studies, it is revealed that employee career development programmes and organisational performance have significant relationship. The result of the first hypothesis revealed that there is a statistically significant and strong positive relationship between career counselling and organisation performance at .005 level of significance ($r=.791, p<.05$), hence the null hypothesis was rejected. The findings were consistent with earlier studies, among which is the study carried out by Ubani et al., (2024), revealed a positive relationship between career counselling and organisation performance in their study. This further reinforces the argument that career counselling helps employees to align personal goals with organisational objectives which in turn lead to improved performance. Consequently, the second hypothesis revealed that there is a statistically positive and significant relationship between career mentoring and organisation performance at .005 level of significance ($r=.723, p<.05$), hence the null hypothesis was rejected. This calls to show that mentoring significantly contributes to the growth and skill development of employees. The findings corroborate with the study by Igudia (2022), the consistency in both this present and earlier study underscores the importance of career mentoring as a strategic developmental program for organisational performance. According to the third hypothesis, the findings revealed that there is a statistically significant and strong positive relationship between career training and organisation performance at .005 level of significance ($r=.752, p<.05$), hence the null hypothesis was rejected. The findings were consistent with earlier studies, among which is the study carried out by Udo et al., (2024) in their study investigated the relationship between career training and employee performance in money deposit banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

All of the results across the three hypotheses further reinforces and aligns with Becker's (1964) human capital theory, which posits that employees who are the human element within an organisation represent valuable assets whose knowledge, skills, and competencies contribute to the success of the organisation; thus, investment in structured career developmental programs helps in building a performance-driven workforce by enhancing the skills, knowledge, and capabilities of employees.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study examined the interplay between employee career development programs and organisational performance in Lagos state, the findings revealed that all three measures of career development; career counselling, mentoring and training have strong positive significant relationship with organisational performance. The result establishes the premises that career development programs play a vital role in enhancing employee capacities, skills, capabilities productivity which inherently improve organisational performance.

Additionally, the findings are consistent with earlier empirical research, supporting the claim that organisations that regularly support their employees' career development typically see higher performance levels. This study confirms the strategic significance of human resource development as a key instrument for gaining a competitive edge in the context of Nigerian organisations. Overall, the study concludes that employee career development programs have a major and positive influence on organisational performance and should be prioritized in today's modern workplaces.

In-line with the above findings and conclusion, the study recommends the following;

- i. Organisations should establish a structured career counselling program that would guide employees in their career path and decision.
- ii. The management should promote career mentoring through formal or informal mentoring schemes so as to strengthen employee development.
- iii. Organisations should continuously invest in career training and development initiatives that equips employees with requisite skills and competencies.

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